

The CEDA vocabulary editor: a new tool for managing controlled vocabularies

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CF Standard Names: A Controlled Vocabulary

CF (Climate and Forecast) standard names are a comprehensive list of terms for describing geophysical parameters in data files. They form one component of the metadata needed to fully describe an environmental dataset. (Other metadata include, for example, the name of the model or observing platform that produced the data). CF metadata were originally designed to describe numerical model data such as those produced by climate prediction or weather forecasting models. Increasingly, however, they are being used to describe observational datasets from instruments as diverse as tide gauges and satellite radiometers. CF metadata have been adopted as the standard in many large scientific projects, such as CMIP5 from which data will be shared by scientists around the world in preparing the next Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change assessment report. CF metadata will also be used to describe satellite data from the next series of NOAA polar orbiting satellites (JPSS) and are even being used to describe data from a model of the Martian climate.

Managing A Controlled Vocabulary

❖ Scientists wishing to write their data in CF-NetCDF files can propose new standard names by sending an email to the CF mailing list. Each proposal should include an explanation of the name's intended meaning and a suggestion of the appropriate units.

❖ All members of the CF community are then invited to submit their comments on the proposal.

❖ The public discussions are moderated by the standard names manager with the aim of reaching a consensus decision on the wording of new names, their explanations and units.

❖ Once agreement is reached on a new name it can be accepted for inclusion in the published standard name table.

A New Tool for Vocabulary Management: The CEDA Vocabulary Editor

❖ When a new CF standard name is proposed an entry is created for it in the vocabulary editor using a web form. The data entry form is security protected so that only those authorized to edit the published vocabulary may effect changes.

❖ A web page shows the progress of all vocabulary terms through the CF acceptance procedures. Colour coded backgrounds give the user a quick way of seeing the current status of each name, e.g. blue means a newly submitted proposal, amber means that a name has been formally accepted.

❖ Once accepted, the editor can be used to simultaneously publish names on the CF website and in the NERC vocabulary server developed at the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC).

The Flow of Data Through the CEDA Vocabulary Editor

A Sample Entry For A CF Standard Name Within the CEDA Vocabulary Editor

Home Vocab List Home Help

Viewing current change requests for vocab list, 'http://vocab.ndg.nerc.ac.uk/list/P071/17'

Created Date	Status	Proposer	Proposed Date	Comment
2011-04-06T14:07:18Z	Accepted	Alison Pamment	2010/11/29	Standardize all mass_content names.

[Mailing list thread](#) [Mass_content_standard_names](#)

Change Date	Term	Description	Units	Units ref	AMIP	GRIB
2006-09-26T17:12:43Z	atmosphere_water_content	"Content" indicates a quantity per unit area. The "atmosphere content" of a quantity refers to the vertical integral from the surface to the top of the atmosphere. For the content between specified levels in the atmosphere, standard names including content_of_atmosphere_layer are used. "Water" means water in all phases.	kg m-2			
2011-04-06T14:07:18Z	atmosphere_mass_content_of_water	"Content" indicates a quantity per unit area. The "atmosphere content" of a quantity refers to the vertical integral from the surface to the top of the atmosphere. For the content between specified levels in the atmosphere, standard names including content_of_atmosphere_layer are used. "Water" means water in all phases.	kg m-2	http://vocab.ndg.nerc.ac.uk/term/P061/37/KMP2		

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